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SIGNIFICANCE OF SPIRITUALITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE BIOPSYCHOSOCIOSPIRITUAL PERSONALITY MODEL

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Abstract

Purpose of research was to examine and analyse whether there is relation between internal self-congruence and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model at middle age period. Additional aim was to make linguistic adaptation of Biopsychosociospiritual model's survey in Latvian culture. Research is mostly based on scientific researches and literature in fields of psychology and medicine. Many research results prove that patients are showing increasing desire to be treated by physicians who are interested in their personality. Every problem a person may face in one's life can be viewed from four aspects – physical, psychological, social and spiritual. Unfortunately not all of these aspects are jointly taken into account in fields of medicine and psychology.

Scope of this research covered several questions: 1. Is there statistically significant relation between internal self-congruence and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model at middle age period? 2. Is there any relation between spirituality and other factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model? 3. Is there any relation between spirituality and internal self- congruence? 4. Are there statistically significant differences between male and female groups when analysing internal self-congruence and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model?

Total of 280 respondents (179 female, 101 male) at age from 25 to 55 years took part in research ($M=40,1$; $SD=7,05$). In order to conduct research Antonovsky's "Sense of Coherence Scale" (Antonovsky Sense of Coherence Scale - SOC, 1987; and "Biopsychosociospiritual Inventory" (Biopsychosociospiritual Inventory (BioPSSI); Katerndahl D., Oyiriaru D., 2007).Results demonstrated that there is statistically significant and close relation between internal self-congruence and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model, statistically significant and close correlation between spirituality and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model, statistically significant and close relation between spirituality and internal self-congruence. It was also discovered that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female groups when analysing internal self-congruence and factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model.

Keywords: sense of coherence, spirituality, spiritual well-being, biopsychosocio-spiritual model, mental and physical health, self - concept

The current period of social change is the time of dramatic alteration of living conditions (devaluation of old, habitual values, instability of social structures, changes in the social environment, loss of social development prospects, destruction of traditional spiritual foundations) on one hand, and, on the other hand, it is a certain stage in the development of state and society. In overcoming everyday difficulties, vitality and spirituality may become the stronghold of individual potential. Resilience characterises the ability of a person to withstand stressful situations. Resilience is a system of beliefs about oneself, about the surrounding world, and about one's relationships with this world. The practical aspect of resilience is determined by the role this per-

sonality factor plays in withstanding stress, and primarily in stressful situations related to professional activity. It is resilience that is the main factor determining the impact of stressogenic factors (including chronic ones) on somatic and spiritual health, as well as on successful functioning.

Nowadays, however, resilience does not build sufficient capacity if in our daily life and life philosophy we turn away from spirituality.

Spiritual knowledge of human nature has been in existence for thousands of years, but both in social life and social sciences, its study has not been sufficiently addressed. Consequently, spirituality is not generally understood as quality, depth, integrity, and harmony of personality (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Schematised picture of understanding

It is expedient to consider spirituality from the point of view of microcosm and macrocosm, thus, expanding and deepening the spectrum of the problems addressed by the psychology of spirituality. We have an approximate understanding of a person as a mechanism, but not as a living (active and free) being. Therefore, the more active and free people are, the worse is our understanding of them.

However, an increasing number of professional psychologists start recognising the need to explore spiritual processes of personality development. The soul is not only a distinctive reality of the natural world, but also a reality with a completely different meaning. The soul is not nature but freedom and the human ultimate value. The spiritual character and spiritual value of a person is determined not only by their psychological nature, but also by the union of freedom of choice with the "spiritual self" of the individual. Examining aspects of human freedom, Berdyaev specially noted its connection with the soul: "The soul is not only freedom but also a meaning. The meaning of the world is spirituality." (Berdyaev, 1993)

If anyone says that life and the world are meaningless, they simultaneously allow for the existence of a meaning which is higher than this life and the world. The soul and spirituality process, transform and give clarity to the natural and historical world, bringing freedom and meaning to it. To remove the spiritual from psychology means to make the psyche (soul, inner world) of a person inanimate and, thus, to stop the evolutionary development of society. If research is not carried out on the "science of spirituality", psychology becomes a 'psychogram' or 'psychography'. The psychology of spirituality does not put a claim to a new position, it only proposes to expand the context and see psychology as a science of soul and personality - as a

living system (Boeree, 2006). Spirituality harmonises the inner world of the individual, and in the external social world, it finds its expression in actions, behaviour, and activities. This expression comes as if objectified in the real world, whereas spiritual revival and its dynamic development take place in the inner world of a person. Spirituality is the life task of man. Paradoxically, the expression of spirituality is realised by the inner spiritual power of a person, and that is why its growth cannot be brought about or facilitated by non-spiritual states. The higher is never born from the lower which does not have any similarity with the higher and its potential. The spiritual development of personality is the actualisation of its capabilities. Life experiences such as, for example, suffering due to illness or poverty, injustice or betrayal, do not contain any spiritual part, but they can nevertheless awake spiritual power in the individual. However, the awakening of spiritual power means that although hidden, in a dormant state, this power has always been in existence. Our spiritual essence is part of human creative power to become aware of the functioning of Supreme Laws in daily processes and of our part in these processes. Answering the question about the source of true spirituality, Berdyaev argued that

Spirituality may not be at the heights of civilisation. It is also important to understand that spirituality is not an absolute antithesis to body or soul - it subjugates both body and soul, and then transforms them. Spirit is first and foremost a liberating and transformative force. A person with a pronounced spirituality is not the one who has departed from the worldly and historical life. Such people are fully involved and actively participating in the worldly and historical life, but they are free from its power and transform it. (Berdyaev, 1993)

Spiritual and unspiritual in the human psyche are important psychological categories of spirituality. These two categories are dichotomous like "alive and dead", "good and bad", "constructive and destructive", and so on. The essence of spiritual life is love, creation and co-creation, whereas unspiritual signifies the absence of love, which in turn breaks a hole in the personal system of protection and prohibits from attaining self-realisation. Evil is not a force, it is only a mockery, and, in the same way, the unspiritual is a distortion of the spiritual. The unspiritual, being a distortion, manifests itself as an imitation of what has already been created, whereas the spiritual is the true creative beginning. The unspiritual is not the only antagonist of the spiritual, there is also a negative emotional attitude towards others. No wonder they say: "There is a thin line between love and hate", or "A heart tired of hate will never learn to love." The personality has been already tired of the negative impact of the external world and the suppression of inner emotional outbursts, so it strives for spiritual rebirth. Social revival is not possible without the spiritual revival of the individual - a restored individual self-actualises and adds spiritual value to society.

In the process of spiritual rebirth, the following prospects of development arise, namely: a) knowledge and awareness of one's multifaceted "I", understanding one's connection with the highest spiritual values, b) self-determination, c) awareness of one's mission and place in life, d) striving for inner harmony. The attainment and appreciation of spiritual gifts expands the boundaries of emotional experience, makes it deeper and more intense. The attainment is based on heightened emotional perception, shared experiences and empathy to others; accumulation of wisdom in the process of acquiring life and spiritual experience, search for the meaning of life; connecting life phenomena, one's self-development and connections with the awareness of the sources of Higher Spirituality; the development of creative individuality as an inimitable, original and unique personality trait, with this creative individuality emerging as an intrinsic value and as a creative potential for self-expression capable of building not only the internal, but also the external world.

Positive experience creates contentment, a sense of security, and provides for acceptance of other people. Often, its acquisition is based in the positive experience of other people (parents, relatives, friends, and acquaintances), and then that kind of experience exists as long as its sources stay. Becoming aware of the nature of positive experience and its acquisition, people can sense power as well as powerlessness, with both feelings hidden from outside. As a result, the less is acquired through one's own force and abilities, the more

this individual is dominated by the shadowy desires of obtaining external power. The need for recognition, the desire to control and influence others are both born from the feeling of fear of one's own powerlessness, the fear of being "oneself", and hence is the desire to be "above the rest". It is particularly evident when people are satisfied with themselves, with their life achievements, with their financial situation and social status; they tend to hold to a belief that they have achieved the top of their spiritual development. However, if the habitual behaviour no longer brings success, if the habitual way of thinking no longer produces the desired result, the person faces an existentialist crisis, which in turn creates negative experience. This negative experience produces fear, dejection, and inability to adequately match the positive attitude of the majority. Negative experience, however, is always unique in entering life uncontrollably and catching us emotionally unaware. We usually assess and judge others. Negative experience affects our feelings and going through it makes us start judging ourselves. We perceive negative experience as definite and affective repeatedly. However, the very experience may serve as a reference point for the genuine spiritual essence of a person. Understanding the experience lends a possibility for creative mental activity to penetrate the realm of spirituality, to reach a new integrative level. Experiencing is a creative process of understanding a separate facet of the spiritual dimension while getting a new perspective of oneself, the situation, people, and things; it teaches to compare oneself with others, to assess the burden of one's experiences, feelings, intentions, and the desire to cope with all of them.

Spiritual development occurs when the consciousness of a person expands, and their productive experience is enriched. With the expansion of the personal sphere of knowledge, not only memory and cognition develop but also perception. The spiritually and ethically significant in a person comes not from the social environment but from the inner essence of the spiritual personality. As the philosopher and Nobel Prize winner Albert Schweitzer noted, "[i]nitially, morality can only arise in the individual. When society has a bigger impact on the individual than the individual on society, there starts the degradation of culture, that is, spiritual and ethical prerequisites are leveled down."

It would be a mistake to look at this as individualism and asociality. On the contrary, it confirms the existence of internal sociality, it also confirms the fact that a person is a social being and can attain full self-realisation only in society. However, a truly good and just human society is possible only if it is formed by spiritually rich and constantly developing personalities (see Fig. 2).

Soul (spirituality) духовный
ОПЫТ, ВОЛЯ)

Spiritual sphere обра-
зования и другие пути

Figure 2. Necessary (optimistic) variant

Carl Gustav Jung drew attention to the particular spiritual drives of a specially gifted person: "To a gifted person, his spiritual drives cover a wide range of contradictions. Thus, giftedness very rarely characterises all spiritual spheres more or less evenly." (Jung, 2021) He also singled out the spiritual functions of giftedness or "abnormally rapid growth", i.e., excessive development of the personality, and specially highlighted "moral giftedness", writing that "a gifted child faces difficulties not only in the intellectual, but also in the moral sphere, i.e., in the realm of senses." Giftedness is not an absolute value - it becomes such only if people strive for and understand universal human values so that they can put their giftedness to good use. Unfortunately, the creative potential can act destructively as well. The fact whether it leads to good or bad is determined only by a spiritually oriented person herself. It is giftedness that has such a moral imperfection that it evokes in its owner a feeling of superiority, and at the same time psychic inflation.

Consequently, the main motive that awakens to life is a *personal strive for self-realisation, the wish for demonstrating one's potential*. Life is an eternal whirl of consciousness, and it manifests in a dynamic exchange of impulses of wisdom between the microcosm and the macrocosm, between the energy-informational field of man and the energy-informational field of the Universe. The urge for creation is ignorance. *Ignorance* is good ground for creativity and freedom. Ignorance may awaken a person and bring openness. Part of the desire and willingness to face the unknown is called *intelligent ignorance*. This means that any life situation requires flexibility, creativity, spontaneity, and spirituality as a zero-base point of personality, and it corresponds to the efforts and creative potential of an individual.

The "spiritual Self" is a merge of the three primary sources, namely, the bodily, mental, and spiritual one, and their mutual growth leads to a spiritual rebirth. In the tradition of humanitarian psychology, they are

called higher or "peak" experiences. As Maslov observed, "almost everyone has lived through higher experiences, but not everyone knows about it" (Maslov, 1995). Modern researchers are preoccupied with the question of the possibility of internal unity or integrity of the human, the question associated with the unity of the social character and the part given by nature. However, "in large part, the great mystery of such a unique unity has not yet been unravelled" (Brushlinsky, 1994).

In the vanguard of the methodology to research the depths of human consciousness is *structured psychosomatics*, which considers phenomena as corresponding to different levels of organisation of human existence (Minchenkov & Elpidiforov, 2002). Structured psychosomatics distinguishes seven levels of logical consciousness and analyses characteristics of each level.

The first *three levels* (perception of the environment, behaviour, self-recognition - the operational level, the division of attention, decision making, etc.) are examined by many sub-branches of psychology. *The first level - the rational level or the oral circuit* - covers bodily efforts to find protection, and it is aimed at bio-survival characteristic of the primitive phase of human evolution, when living conditions are cruel. Modern wars, cultural anomie, criminogenic environment, the power of money, and other factors keeps this circuit in continuous tension and fear. *The second level - dual-emotional level* - determines the territorial contour, which is dominated by the politics of power, political machinations, and, contrarily, patriotic orientation. The neurostructure of this circuit is controlled by emotions. As representatives of the psychosomatic approach point out, modern man is robotic, that is, he is caught in certain reflexes. False logical attitudes (e.g., irreconcilability, fanaticism, boastfulness, cowardice, etc.) very easily enter the semantic structure because survival instincts signal danger. *The third is the rational level* or the territorial semantic contour of the rational mind. The power of this circuit is in language.

Words have *denotations* that relate to the sensory-existential world, and *connotations* - emotional colouring (in a poetic and rhetorical aspect). A person can be influenced by words. This is called *neophobia* - a person's fear of new semantic signals, as the new has no meaning and correspondence in the real world. Here lies the effect of demagoguery, advertising, and cults. All riches are created by the neurons of the human mind - accurate information. This wealth comprises artifacts that improve a person's life.

The fourth logical level of consciousness is associated with the system of faith, values, and beliefs of an individual, through which the individual implements his life strategies. This level can be designated as a sociosexual circuit. The sociosexual level is activated in youth, and it awakens the sexual mechanism. By examining this circuit, one can find out which "*fetishes*" are involved and how they are represented. This semantic circuit of the nervous system stores most sexual failures, the feeling of guilt, and prohibitions.

The fifth logical level of consciousness is the highest level of the integration of experience, the level of generalisation of abstractions and worldviews. Consciousness and attention are mostly drawn to internal processes, and the external is perceived through the internal paradigm. This level forms a holistic neurosomatic circuit. Such phenomena as *cure by faith*, *placebo effect*, *mythical rejuvenation*, ecstasy, etc., have been known for thousands of years. They are called psychosomatic or neurosomatic effects. At this level operates conscience, which is an important category of the psychology of spirituality. Conscience is the *voice of spirituality*, our moral stress.

The fifth holistic neurosomatic level controls the right hemisphere of the brain; it is healing and global, and it operates with *gestalts*. This level is often used by various sects that engage in neurosomatic '*brainwashing*'. In this process, there are several stages, namely: 1) *isolation* (from the family, from the former place of residence); 2) *psychological submission* to the community (guru) and up to the childlike state in order to imprint a new state of submissiveness; 3) *free love*, sexual games, which are mainly supported by drugs (85% of marijuana is used to enhance erotic feelings); 4) *neurosomatic ecstasy*, which is 'gifted by the guru'. Only simpletons do not understand that they can go through all these stages on their own.

The sixth and seventh levels are the stages of self-identification and projection of the Absolute with one's personality transiting to the next level, searching for self-discovery and the meaning of life, an absolute saturation - all in all, the process of one's creative, spiritual knowledge and realisation. The sixth level is the collective neurogenetic level or circuit in which the brain operates when the nervous system sends signals from individual neurons, forming neurogenetic connections. The neurogenetic consciousness is the genetic archive of a person, the DNA archives possible and accessible in an active state of consciousness. This is the entrance to the realm of the unconscious, which allows you to talk with your "architect of evolution".

The development of psychosomatics (*soma* - body, soul, spirit), together with the psychology of spirituality (noetics), offers a way to channel the personality and understand its holistic, integrative essence, which is inconceivable without creativity and spirituality. Nowadays, the existential crisis or the crisis of the meaning of life makes us think of the effectiveness of technological civilisation (wars, environmental resources, food problems, etc.); the crisis of worldview does not rouse one to accept one's responsibility as a spiritually creative challenge. "Spiritual connection occurs through enhanced perception, awareness, understanding, and product as an expression of God's will and Higher Intelligence. 'Direct connection or contact' manifests itself as an inexhaustible source of Divine light or a merge with the Higher Intelligence, with the soul of the Universe, which occurs in a state of peace, reconciliation, and complete safety." (Carrette, Jeremy, 2013)

Problems psychology has with the study of spirituality are justified by the fact that it is difficult to conduct an experiment related to the scale of the studied phenomena in time and space, the scale presenting obstacles to observation and diagnosis. Spiritual manifestations and spiritual mechanisms of mental phenomena permeate the entire mental life of the individual. However, the significance of the study of the psychic side of spiritual phenomena is heightened by the fact that its subjective value may turn out to be higher than that of the phenomena traditionally studied by psychology such as, for example, attention, feelings, values, etc. "Spirituality is a constitutive feature: the human has a spiritual as well as a bodily and mental components, whereas animals have only the latter two, with the spiritual being a distinguishable characteristic of people, a uniquely human trait. A human being starts to behave human only if he can overcome the level of psychophysicality of his body and treat himself so as not to hinder his progress" (Frankl, 2010).

The spirituality of the creative existence of a person not just characterises human existence, but, most likely, constitutes a person as a creator. It is this possibility which is being or existence, and existence demands one constantly go beyond one's own boundaries and into spirituality (Vidnere, 2015).

In the United States, there have been conducted studies which demonstrated the significance of mental abilities and spiritual development in the life of an adult. Spirituality is closely related to mental, emotional, and physical health (Wink, & Dillon, 2002; Wilber, 2006). In psychology, this integrative approach is associated with 'self-concept'.

If the inner core - 'self-concept' - is in balance, then a person can live with a sense of coherence, feel healthy and happy. However, spirituality or spiritual growth is essential for inner balance, as without it a person cannot be in harmony and in balance (Frankel, & Quill, 2005).

Antonovsky (1996) defines the sense of coherence as a sense of global perception of life characterising the level at which a person holds a continuous and dynamic belief in the availability of resources and has knowledge of life requirements (Antonovsky, 1996).

Antonovsky's concept of the sense of coherence is characterised by the three components, namely, the cognitive, instrumental, and motivational one.

In psychosomatics, along with the self-concept, American psychiatrist George Engel originally developed the Biopsychosocial model (Engel, 1977, 2005), the model evaluating biopsychosociospiritual factors, functions and state of health. The model determines that diseases and health are both the result of the interaction of psychological, social, and spiritual factors.

Thus, *the research goal* is to find out the existence of links between spirituality, a sense of coherence, and

factors of the self-concept model in the middle age. The study participants are 280 respondents.

The research methods: to measure the sense of coherence, the Sense of Coherence Scale (SOC) (Antonovsky, 1987) was used; to measure the dimensions of the self-concept, there was used the Biopsychosociospiritual Inventory (BioPSSI) (Katerndahl & Oyiriaru, 2007) adapted by Rigase and Vidnere (2015).

To determine whether there is a statistically significant relationship between the Cronbach's alpha of the Biopsychosociospiritual dimensions and statistical indicators in the period of middle adulthood, the correlation coefficient was calculated (see Table 1).

Table 1.

<i>Factors of Biopsychosociospiritual model</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mnd</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>E</i>
Physical factors	0,96	14,45	7,87	20	4	33	0,69	-0,36
Psychological factors	0,96	10,28	3,64	18	7	17	0,40	-1,35
Social factors	0,98	20,01	7,46	36	8	30	-0,32	-1,40
Spiritual factors	0,97	19,58	6,42	34	8	28	-0,49	-0,98
Functional factors	0,96	21,25	10,59	25	4	42	0,41	-0,70

Note: N=120

Summarising the results, it can be concluded that the obtained indicators of the Cronbach's alpha of the biopsychosociospiritual dimensions are quite high. For the scales "physical factors" and "psychological factors", $a=0.96$, for the scale "social factors", $a=0.98$, for the scale "spiritual factors", $a=0.97$, and for the scale "functional factors", $a=0.96$.

To determine whether there is a statistically significant relationship between the factors of the sense of coherence and the biopsychosociospiritual model in the period of middle adulthood, the correlation coefficients were calculated (see Table 2).

Table 2.

<i>Factors in BioPSSI</i>	Sense of Meaning in Life	Sense of Resilience	Feeling of vitality
Physical factors	-0,74**	-0,67**	-0,68**
Psychological factors	-0,72**	-0,61**	-0,62**
Social factors	0,76**	0,69**	0,68**
Spiritual factors	0,78**	0,78**	0,70**
Functional factors	-0,79**	-0,73**	-0,72**

Note: N=120. ** $p < 0,01$

Summarising the results, it can be concluded that there is a high correlation between different dimensions of the biopsychosociospiritual model. Thus, there is a high positive correlation between the indicators of the sense of coherence, namely, between the sense of meaning in life and spiritual factors ($r=0.78$, $p < 0.01$). Further, there is a high positive correlation between the sense of resilience and spiritual factors ($r=0.78$, $p < 0.01$), and the feeling of vitality ($r=-0.70$, $p < 0,01$).

To determine whether there is any correlation between the spiritual factors and other factors of the bi-

opsychosociospiritual model, a linear regression analysis was performed. The results showed that a statistically significant relationship exists between the spiritual factors and social factors ($\beta=0.40$, $p < 0.01$) and between the spiritual factors and functional factors ($\beta=0.41$, $p < 0.01$). This means that when the factorial sign (functional factors) changes by the value of its standard deviation, the resulting sign (spiritual factor) will decrease by 0.40 of the standard deviation (see Table 3).

Table 3.

Regression Analysis Results

Variables	B	B	
Physical factors	-0,084	-0,105	
Psychological factors	-0,167	-0,094	
Social factors	0,336	,402**	
Fuinctional factors	-0,238	- 0,40**	
Constant = 20,77			
R ² = 0,99			
Adapted R ² = 0,99			

Note: N = 280. * $p < 0,05$, ** $p < 0,01$.

To determine the relationship between the spiritual dimension and the sense of coherence, a linear regression analysis was carried out (see Table 4).

The results showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between the spiritual dimension

and the sense of meaning in life ($\beta=1.05$, $p<0.01$). This means that the change of the factorial sign (a scale of the sense of meaning in life) to the value of its standard deviation, will increase by 1.06 of the standard deviation.

Table 4

Regression Analysis Results

Variables	B	β
Sense of Meaning in Life	0,63	1,06**
Sense of Resilience	-0,13	-0,17
Feeling of vitality	-0,09	-0,10
Constant = -0,89		
R ² = 0,6		
Adapted R ² = 0,59		

Note: N = 280. ** $p < 0,01$.

The results of the study demonstrate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the sense of coherence and the factors of the biopsychosociospiritual model or the self-concept, with the spirituality of the individual closely related to their inner harmony.

Next, the results of the study showed that there is a statistically significant correlation between the spiritual dimension and other factors of the biopsychosociospiritual model. The results conform to the results of the previous studies indicating the relationship of spirituality with long-term health improvement, including in groups with such problems as alcohol misuse, smoking, drugs, and other similar ones (Sulmasy, 2002).

Lastly, the results showed that a statistically significant relationship exists between the spiritual dimension and social and functional ones, which is in agreement with the theory that spirituality causes a significant effect on the state of human health (both physical and spiritual), on the daily life of a person, and the quality of life in general (Katerndahl, & Oyiriaru, 2007; Vidnere, Nucho, 2009; Sperry, & Shafranske, 2005). In addition, the obtained results conform to the theory that socially active, communicable people have the closest connection with spirituality (Wink, & Dillon, 2002; Vidnere, 2015).

The results of the study confirmed that the biopsychosociospiritual model reflects the self-concept of the individual.

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